

4TH EUROCC VILNIUS HACKATHON & WORKSHOP ON USING HPC

Abstract book

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June 27, 2025

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Welcome

We are pleased to welcome you to the “**4th EuroCC Vilnius Hackathon and Workshop on Using HPC**”, organized by the Lithuanian National Competence Centre (NCC Lithuania) under the EuroCC4SEE (EuroCC2) project. This event brings together researchers and practitioners from various fields to explore advanced topics in High-Performance Computing (HPC), featuring both scientific presentations and hands-on challenges.

The program highlights cutting-edge applications of HPC across diverse domains, including astrophysics, quantum chemistry, molecular dynamics, and machine learning. Several contributions will showcase research conducted on the Vilnius University supercomputer "VU HPC" Saulėtekis at the Faculty of Physics, as well as on EuroHPC facilities managed by the **Open Access Center “HPC Saulėtekis”**.

We also encourage open discussions on strengthening academia – industry collaboration and sharing best practices through consultation hours, hackathon tasks, coffee breaks, and networking activities.

We wish you inspiring talks, productive collaboration, and engaging networking experiences.

Assoc. Prof. Mindaugas Mačernis

(on behalf of the organizing & scientific committee).

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Mindaugas Mačernis', with a large circular flourish on the left side.

June 27, 2025

Program

Friday, June 27

8:30–11:00	REGISTRATION (UNTIL 11:00)	
9:00–9:45	Mindaugas Mačernis	Consultation hour on HPC usage
9:45–10:45		Hackathon hour on using HPC and EuroHPC resources. Task: to make an HPC application
10:45–11:00	COFFEE BREAK	
11:00–11:05	Mindaugas Mačernis	Welcome words
11:05–11:30	Mindaugas Mačernis	Large Language Models for HPC research
11:30–12:00	Mindaugas Macernis <i>(Keynote speaker)</i>	Carotenoids study Challenges for Modeling Raman and Absorption Spectra
12:00–12:50	LUNCH	
12:50–13:00	GROUP PHOTO	
	SESSION CHAIR: LAURA BALIULYTĖ	
13:00–13:30	Darius Abramavičius <i>(Keynote speaker)</i>	Dynamics of excitation from excitons to polarons in molecular complexes
13:30–13:50	Stepas Toliautas	Quantum-chemical exploration of the methanol-sensing mechanism of the meso-formyl BODIPY compounds
13:50–14:10	Alytis Gruodis	Feed-Forward Neural Network for Predicting Engine Combustion Parameters
14:10–14:30	Eimantas Urniežius	Modeling of molecular nanotubes and their optical spectra
14:30–14:45	Dmitrij Semionov	Modeling dynamics of open clusters using NBody6
14:45–15:00	COFFEE BREAK	
	SESSION CHAIR: MINDAUGAS MAČERNIS	
15:00–15:30	Kęstutis Aidas <i>(Keynote speaker)</i>	QM/MD and NMR study of aqueous mixtures of choline lysinate
15:30–15:50	Žyginta Murnikova	Peptide in [Emim][TFA] Mixtures with Water – Theoretical Study of Structural and NMR Properties
15:50–16:10	Einaras Sipavičius	Structural characterization and accurate 1H NMR spectra modelling of [C4mim][BF4] ionic liquid and its aqueous mixtures
16:10–16:30	Jonas Franukevičius	Molecular Dynamics Statistical Analysis: Probabilistic Modeling of Molecular Geometry from MD Data
16:30–16:45	Amina Elkady	Modeling the structure and NMR spectra of amantadine encapsulated in supramolecular matrices
16:45–17:00	Rokas Dobužinskas	Structural Characterization of trans-Stilbene in Polystyrene Films via X-ray Diffraction
17:00–19:00	NETWORKING / DINNER	

Large Language Models for HPC research

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In this short workshop session, we will explore the internal anatomy of large language models (LLMs) and their practical use in high-performance computing (HPC) environments. The talk will cover effective prompting strategies, performance considerations, and the basics of LLM evaluation. We will also examine how LLMs can act as evaluators themselves, discuss methods for uncertainty quantification, and introduce intermediate techniques for reasoning assessment and benchmarking.

This session draws upon key insights from ISC25 – the International Supercomputing Conference 2025, a premier global event focused on high-performance computing, machine learning, and computational science. Attendees will receive a concise, up-to-date overview grounded in the latest conference findings, tailored for immediate application in advanced computational research and engineering contexts.

Carotenoids study Challenges for Modeling Raman and Absorption Spectra

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Carotenoids are naturally occurring pigments with diverse and essential biological functions, particularly in light-harvesting and photoprotection during photosynthesis [1-3]. They contribute to the coloration of leaves, fruits, flowers, and various organisms. The photophysical properties of carotenoids are closely related to those of polyene chains, making them a useful model for understanding excited-state dynamics. Accurate characterization of their excited-state energies and structures is crucial for elucidating the mechanisms of light absorption involving chlorophylls, carotenoids, and related pigments. However, the dynamics observed in Raman and absorption spectra remain incompletely understood [1-3]. Moreover, computational challenges remain in achieving consistency between theoretical predictions and experimental results [4].

We investigated LYC/ β -CD complexes using molecular dynamics (MD) and compared the results with experimental Raman spectra of LYC/HP-CD (Fig.1) [3]. The Raman ν_1 band shifts depending on lycopene's position within the β -CD cavity. Using density functional theory (DFT) and ADC(n) methods, we calculated molecular structures, Raman spectra, and excited-state energy diagrams for various carotenoids and polyenes. For fucoxanthin in methanol, MD simulations combined with QM/MM (DFT) reveal a redshift in the lowest optically allowed transition (Fig. 2). The possible supramolecular complexes and their spectroscopic signatures are discussed.

Fig. 1. Lycopene complex with β -cyclodextrin.

Fig. 2. Fucoxanthin QM/MM simulation

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Dynamics of excitation from excitons to polarons in molecular complexes

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A standard model of excitation in tightly coupled molecular aggregate is the Frenkel exciton model. The main feature of the model is the emergence of collective coherent electronic excitations, which are delocalized due to resonant intermolecular couplings. Intramolecular vibrations introduce exciton decoherence and localization of the excitons, what is often denoted as self-trapping.

Harmonic model of molecular vibrations (Fig. 1) yields the Holstein model Hamiltonian, which has the bilinear form of the exciton-vibration interactions – the vibrational coordinate induces the excitation energy fluctuations. However, the exciton excited states are not thermalized states, so they are poor reference set of states, when coupling to vibrations is strong. Polaron transformation yields different set of states, which are equilibrated with respect to the static phonons, however they may poorly reflect dynamical effects. Partial polaron transformation [1] allows for fine tuning between the exciton and polaron models.

Choosing right reference states may yield rapidly converging equations of motion for the excitation dynamics. A closed new set of equations, based on the Nonlinear Exciton Equations [2] is derived for exciton-polaron dynamics. The equations allow for explicit n-particle quantum model for a exciton-vibrational systems.

Fig. 1 harmonic model of molecular vibration: E0-E4 denote five lowest energy states of an oscillator, which would be included in five-particle quantum model.

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Quantum-chemical exploration of the methanol-sensing mechanism of the *meso*-formyl BODIPY compounds

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Molecular compounds based on the boron-dipyrromethene (BODIPY) group have been shown to have promising potential for use as microscopic, single-molecule optical (fluorescence lifetime-based) sensors of environment properties, such as temperature or viscosity. The compounds exhibit complex energy-relaxation behavior depending on the surroundings, which necessitates both experimental and theoretical research of their own properties [1].

A recent study conjectured how a *meso*-formyl BODIPY derivative (Fig. 1) could act as an optical sensor for cellular viscosity and methanol concentration in the molecule's vicinity. However, an attempt to increase the fluorescence wavelength for better compatibility with biological samples (by changing the molecular structure) resulted in the loss of both polarity and viscosity sensitivity [2].

In this work, a theoretical investigation of the excitation-induced processes of *meso*-formyl BODIPY variants in methanol [3] is continued, assessing the experimental claims and trying to answer questions like: how a non-emissive molecule is a fluorescence-lifetime target? how would it benefit from a reaction with textbook barrier energy comparable to that of the optical excitation? ...and others.

The research is supported by the Research Council of Lithuania (LMT grant no. S-MIP-23-48). Quantum-chemical computations were performed using resources at the supercomputer "VU HPC" of Vilnius University in the Faculty of Physics location [4].

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of *meso*-formyl BODIPY derivatives.

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Feed-Forward Neural Network for Predicting Engine Combustion Parameters

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Predicting fuel combustion modes in engines is a very important area of urban planning. The correct choice of combustible mixtures allows solving many problems, such as more efficient transport operations, lower emissions, utilization of combustible waste oils, etc. Unfortunately, determining the correct fuel proportions requires a lot of experimentation and inefficient combustion in engines.

When solving the problem - how to select mixtures of appropriate proportions according to the desired energy or ecological parameters, only the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) allows for an operational response in a wide dynamic range. Several realizations of ANN [1][2] were used for predictions of following parameters: CO, CO₂, O₂, HC, NO_x concentrations, smokiness, Brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC), Brake thermal efficiency (BTE). Experimental values of excess air ratio, Brake mean effective pressure (BMEP), EGR ratio, start of injection (SOI), cetane number, engine speed, volume fraction of HVO and D100, C/H, Lower heating value (LHV), density were used for input. Architecture of ANN was adjusted according to Ref. [3]. Several successful predictions were described in Refs. [4][5][6].

Fig. 1. VALLUM01 [2] as realization of Feed-Forward Neural Network: input layer consists of P units, output layer consists of R units, single hidden layer consists of Q perceptrons.

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Modeling of molecular nanotubes and their optical spectra

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Large organic molecular aggregates have promising applications as nonlinear optical elements, active materials in photodynamic therapy, and other photonic technologies [1]. In particular, the porphyrin TPPS4 forms two zwitterionic species (Z1 and Z2) at $pH = 1$, which self-assemble into molecular nanotubes that can exist in left-handed (M) or right-handed (P) forms, exhibiting notable optical properties [2]. Although the macroscopic structure of these nanotubes is well studied, their microscopic structure - including the molecular orientation - remains poorly understood. This study develops a theoretical model of these nanotubes and employs the Frenkel excitonic framework to optimize their microscopic arrangement by reproducing their linear optical spectra.

The nanotube is modeled by constructing a 2D crystal lattice with a constant of $a = 9.3 \text{ \AA}$, which is then rolled into a cylinder to form a tubular lattice of equally spaced points. A molecule is assigned to each point, each with four optical transition energies (two for the B band and two for the Q band), characterized by optical transition dipole vectors. Due to the molecule's planar symmetry, all dipole vectors lie within a defined molecular plane, whose orientation is described by a normal vector \mathbf{n} . Optical spectra are calculated by constructing the nanotube's Hamiltonian and solving the stationary Schrödinger equation to determine transition energies and wavefunctions. Optimization of the molecular plane's orientation is achieved by introducing two parameters, α_1 and α_2 , which rotate the plane of each molecule relative to its lattice site.

By fitting simulated absorption spectra to experimental data, optimal values of $\alpha_1 = 32^\circ$ and $\alpha_2 = 26^\circ$ were obtained. In addition to absorption, circular dichroism (CD) spectra were calculated for both M and P-type nanotubes in the B band, yielding results that closely match experimental measurements. Furthermore, spectra of partially formed nanotubes were simulated, revealing the dynamic evolution of spectral peaks with increasing tube size and number of windings. To improve the model's accuracy, the effects of diagonal disorder were also incorporated into the spectral calculations.

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Modeling dynamics of open clusters using NBody6

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A problem of dynamical evolution of open star clusters is a complex one as it deals with both internal and external factors. Many, if not most nearby star clusters display signatures of interaction history [1]. To establish possible causes of these signatures we use NBody6 code [2,3], simulating gravitational interaction in systems consisting of up to 10^6 massive particles. This program is well suited for a variety of problems and computational architectures, implementing both CPU and GPU acceleration through parallelization schemes. By computing a model bank, covering a range of interaction between an isolated open star cluster and common Galactic disk objects, including close encounters with molecular clouds and passage of the Galactic plane, we intent to establish dynamical history of several open star clusters, currently located in the Perseus-Cygnus inter-arm region of our Galaxy.

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QM/MD and NMR study of aqueous mixtures of choline lysinate

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Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations combined with the quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) models have proven to be a powerful computational technique for accurate predictions of electronic properties of extensive molecular systems. MD simulations are employed to sample the phase space of molecular system of interest under specific thermodynamic conditions, and then QM/MM calculations of electronic properties are performed where the central part of the molecular system is described by an electronic structure method and the rest of the system is modelled by a classical force field.

Aiming to scrutinize intermolecular organization in aqueous mixtures of choline lysinate, [Cho][Lys], ionic liquid (IL), the dependences of the ¹H NMR chemical shifts and diffusion coefficients on their composition were measured [1]. To rationalize experimental findings, extensive MD simulations and linear-response QM/MM computations of NMR shielding constants were performed. Analysis of MD trajectories reveals that extent of intermolecular contacts between cations and anions intensifies with the increasing content of the IL in the mixture. Moreover, the tendency of choline cations and the side chains of lysinate anions to self-aggregate was observed as well, leading to the formation of a continuous, highly polar domain composed of choline cations and the carboxylate groups of lysinate anions, as well as a less polar domain formed by the side chains of the anions in IL-rich mixtures. Under these circumstances, isolated water pockets are found to be situated at the interface of the polar and nonpolar ionic domains. The dependences of the measured diffusion coefficients on the composition of the mixture reveals the existence of two dynamical regimes – fast and slow regimes below and above molar fraction of the IL of 11%, respectively. Results of MD simulations suggest that – at this specific molar composition of aqueous [Cho][Lys] mixture – continuous water network ceases giving way to the continuous structure of ionic domains being formed. The QM/MM results for the ¹H NMR chemical shifts of aqueous IL mixtures generally agree well with experimental findings and corroborate structural results. The prominent upfield shift of the NMR signal of protons in fast exchange with the rising content of the IL was successfully rationalized [1].

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Peptide in [Emim][TFA] Mixtures with Water – Theoretical Study of Structural and NMR Properties

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Ionic liquids (ILs) have been known as “green” and biocompatible solvents for quite some time and some of their possible biological uses include changing catalytic activity of enzymes, stabilizing or destabilizing various proteins, as well as making them permeate more easily through membranes [1]. The nature of ILs and proteins interactions varies and is difficult to evaluate, so smaller peptides are often used as a model system to discover how different ILs interact with said peptides and change their structure in the aqueous solution. The method most suited for recognizing intermolecular interactions is nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy as atoms, especially hydrogen, chemical shift is very sensitive to changes of central molecule’s close environment.

Fig. 1. Structural formulas of a) peptide Ala-Glu-Pro-Phe, b) ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate, c) *trans/cis* isomeric forms of AEPF

In this work an Ala-Glu-Pro-Phe tetrapeptide (AEPF) was investigated using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics calculations, while in an aqueous environment and in IL/water mixture. An ionic liquid consisting of a popular imidazolium cation and trifluoroacetic acid – ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate ([Emim][TFA]) was chosen. This peptide exists in two different isomers due to proline amino acid – *cis* or *trans*, both of them were evaluated. Theoretically computed chemical shift differences of peptide’s hydrogen atoms were compared to experimental results [2] allowing us to evaluate the different interactions taking place in peptide/IL/water systems, while MD simulation data revealed some structural changes in the peptide’s structure itself. Multiple peptide conformations were found in IL/water mixture, leading to an extensive analysis of structure, intermolecular interactions and IL’s influence on them.

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Structural characterization and accurate ^1H NMR spectra modelling of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{BF}_4]$ ionic liquid and its aqueous mixtures

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Accurate prediction of spectroscopic features of ionic liquids is challenging because of its nanosegregated intermolecular structure, especially in their mixtures with water. Our previous work [1] showed that NMR calculations of C_4mim^+ cation ionic liquids tend to underestimate chemical shift of protons at 2nd position (H2, see Fig. 1 a). We report first accurate prediction of C_4mim^+ NMR spectra in $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{BF}_4]$ ionic liquid (IL) and water mixtures (see Fig. 1 b), including the characterization of intermolecular structure of such systems, especially the local structure around C_4mim^+ using radial and angular (Fig. 1 c) distributions. Results were achieved performing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations on four $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{BF}_4]:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures, ranging from 17 % to 100 % IL molar fraction (χ_{IL}), and then extracting 100 configurations from MD trajectories and conducting quantum mechanics / molecular mechanics (QM/MM) calculations for ^1H NMR shielding constant evaluation.

We would like to thank to "HPC Sauletekis" for providing us computational resources and Research Council of Lithuania for funding (project no. S-MIP-22-74).

Fig. 1. $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{BF}_4]$ chemical structure (a), comparison of calculated and experimental ^1H NMR chemical shifts of C_4mim^+ cation relative to H10 protons in the butyl chain in $\chi_{\text{IL}} = 50\%$ system (b), angular distribution of BF_4^- anions around C2–H2 bond of C_4mim^+ cation in $\chi_{\text{IL}} = 50\%$ system (c).

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Molecular Dynamics Statistical Analysis: Probabilistic Modeling of Molecular Geometry from MD Data

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We introduce *Molecular Dynamics Statistical Analysis* (MDSA), an algorithm designed to statistically characterize the internal geometries of molecular systems from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. MDSA provides a method for analyzing and representing the distribution of internuclear distances sampled from MD trajectories.

The algorithm operates in three stages. First, MDSA computes the uncorrelated probability densities for all pairwise internuclear distances, averaged over the MD simulation time. In the second stage, MDSA constructs a *Linear Combination of Gaussian Models* (LCGM) to approximate the joint distribution of the D -dimensional internuclear distance space. The LCGM comprises of preselected number of D -dimensional Gaussian distributions, where the amplitudes, means and standard deviations are optimized to best match the probability densities derived from the MD data and lastly, the inferred structures from Gaussian models are reformatted to Euclidean geometries and then compared to MD data.

The optimization is guided by a cost function composed of two terms. The first term quantifies the fidelity of the fit through the integral of squared differences between the MD-derived probability density and that generated by the LCGM. The second term is a *realizability cost*, which penalizes Gaussian models that do not correspond to physically possible three-dimensional molecular structures. This realizability cost is computed by evaluating the Gram matrix corresponding to a given configuration of internuclear distances (as defined by the Gaussian model parameters). A valid configuration requires that the Gram matrix is positive semi-definite and has rank exactly three, ensuring that the distances define a realizable molecular geometry in Euclidean space [1].

Fig. 1. P-P distance time dependence (violet) extracted from CH(PPh₂)₂ molecular dynamics data.

Fig. 2. Calculated probability density from MD data (violet) and its LCGM counterpart (green).

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MODELING THE STRUCTURE AND NMR SPECTRA OF AMANTADINE ENCAPSULATED IN SUPRAMOLECULAR MATRICES

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Cavitands (or synthetic receptors) are supramolecular compounds with an enclosed cavity capable of binding small molecules—an attribute that makes them promising for diagnostic applications in biological fluids. Experiments reveal that carbohydrate-based cavitands selectively encapsulate certain alkylammonium compounds, such as drug amantadine, shifting its ¹H NMR signals into the negative region (relative to tetramethylsilane) [1]. This distinct spectral shift highlights the potential of cavitands for metabolomic analyses.

Fig. 1. tetrakis- β -D-glucosyl cavitand–protonated amantadine complex

In this project, the tetrakis- β -D-glucosyl cavitand–protonated amantadine complex is investigated using classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, combined with hybrid quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) methods. Classical MD allows exploration of large-scale molecular behavior under defined thermodynamic conditions, while QM/MM calculations accurately capture electronic effects crucial for NMR shielding. By averaging over configurations from the MD trajectory, temperature-dependent influences are also included. Moreover, the computed NMR spectrum shows good agreement with experimental data, confirming the reliability of this modeling approach. This integrated approach advances our understanding of cavitand–drug interactions and underpins future applications of synthetic cavitands in biomedical diagnostics.

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Structural Characterization of trans-Stilbene in Polystyrene Films via X-ray Diffraction

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The aggregation behavior of trans-stilbene in polymer matrices has recently attracted attention due to its impact on the optical and structural properties of hybrid organic materials. Previous studies have demonstrated that increasing the concentration of trans-stilbene in polystyrene (PS) films induces a transition from molecular dispersion to microcrystalline aggregation, significantly altering fluorescence lifetimes and spectral features [1]. However, the crystallographic characteristics of these aggregates remain underexplored.

In this work, we present X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements of thin films composed of polystyrene and trans-stilbene mixtures, prepared by solution casting onto zero-background substrates. The films were analyzed using a sealed 2 kW X-ray tube and a silicon strip detector in a θ - θ geometry. Diffraction patterns were recorded for various stilbene concentrations (5–80%, where 100% corresponds to a 1:1 mass ratio of stilbene to PS). The results reveal the emergence of distinct diffraction peaks at higher concentrations, consistent with the formation of microcrystalline domains previously observed via CARS and AFM microscopy [2].

Fig. 1. Planes observed (001, 002, 004 and 006) of the pure stilbene depicted in primitive crystal lattice

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Group photo

